

Functional neural mechanisms and underlying structural changes are associated with treatment efficacy in amblyopia.

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Synopsis

Motivation: Elucidating the mechanisms underlying treatment response in amblyopia patients is essential for the development of more efficacious and individualized therapeutic approaches.

Goal(s): The utilization of functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and diffusion imaging in predicting treatment response among patients with amblyopia.

Approach: We utilized diffusion and resting-state fMRI methodologies in pre- and post-treatment assessments for amblyopic patients to evaluate functional and structural changes.

Results: The efficacy of occlusion therapy was indicative of functional homogeneity in ROI connectivity analysis, and changes within the fractional anisotropy were complementary to underlying functional connectivity.

Impact: By integrating imaging parameters and identifying predictive factors for treatment response, it is possible to develop more efficacious and individualized treatment strategies for patients with amblyopia. The functional-structural correlates observed in the study suggest treatment response efficacy.

Introduction

Amblyopia affects visual acuity and ocular alignment, also referred to as lazy eye. In this condition, one eye exhibits delayed development, which results in decreased vision due to anisotropic image formation at the cornea [1]. The efficacy of treatment varies according to age of onset, and early diagnosis and intervention are critical in paediatric cases. Amblyopia is frequently treated with occlusion therapy. However, not all patients respond to this treatment modality, and the mechanisms underlying treatment response remain incompletely understood [2]. Elucidating the neural mechanisms of treatment can facilitate the development of more effective and personalized treatment strategies [3,4]. The objective of this study is to investigate the potential utilization of integrating functional MRI and diffusion imaging as biomarkers for predicting treatment response in amblyopia patients. This approach aims to identify predictive factors for treatment response and stratify populations that may be non-responsive to occlusion therapy at early stages.

Method

A study was conducted on 20 amblyopia patients (mean age: 10 years, standard deviation: 3 years). All patients underwent baseline investigations including cycloplegic refraction, visual acuity, contrast sensitivity, color vision, stereoacuity, and optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) imaging. Similar investigations were conducted at 6 months, with a threshold of 2-line visual acuity improvement considered as the minimum response to treatment.

Data acquisition: Magnetic resonance imaging (3D T1), diffusion tensor imaging (DTI), and resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging (rsfMRI) studies were conducted using a 3 T MR scanner (Ingenia 3.0T TX, M/s. Philips Medical Systems) equipped with a 32-channel head coil. Blood-oxygen-level-dependent (BOLD) imaging was performed utilizing a single-shot echo planar imaging sequence with 45 slices of 3.0 mm isovoxel, flip angle = 65°, transverse orientation, fold-over direction: AP, field of view = 230 mm, TR/TE = 1000/25 ms, number of dynamics = 300, and multiband factor of 3. Diffusion tensor imaging was acquired using B values of 0 and 1000, with a slice thickness of 2 mm, TR/TE = 4797/92 ms, in 32 directions with NSA = 2.

Data analysis: Diffusion tensor imaging and connectome analysis were conducted utilizing the DSI Studio Connectome Analysis toolbox. The groups were classified as response versus no-response. Resting-state functional connectivity was assessed using the CONN toolbox (Ver. 22) with ROI-to-ROI analysis employing the General

Linear Model and correlation. Results are presented with Holm-Bonferroni correction and at $p < 0.05$, FDR corrected. The ROI network analysis was categorized between response versus non-response contrast.

Result

Out of 20 subjects, 14 were selected for study 7 each in responder/non-responders groups, with 6 subjects discarded due to motion artifacts. In ROI analysis, non-responder groups exhibited heterogeneous clusters in comparison to responders, which demonstrated homogeneous interhemispheric clusters at baseline. Furthermore, at follow-up, a significant negative correlation was observed between the default mode and frontal parietal areas within non-responders, in contrast to responders who exhibited improvement in connectivity strength (Figure 1). The visual network was positively localized across the attention network in responders compared to non-responders (Figure 2). Similarly, in DTI connectome tractography, changes in the corpus callosum region in non-responders and the superior longitudinal fasciculus in responders were observed with a significance of $FDR < 0.001$ (Figure 3).

Discussion

Heterogeneity in non-responders and homogeneity in responders observed in ROI connectivity analysis represent hemispheric alterations, which may suggest that treatment efficacy improves connectome strength, potentially providing insight into amblyopia progression intervention methods. Additionally, the diffusion changes observed across the same group present alterations in white matter areas, which complement functional connectivity. In non-responders, changes in the corpus callosum may influence Default Mode and Frontoparietal areas, negatively impacting visual connectivity. Similarly, the Superior longitudinal fasciculus may be associated with an increase in dorsal attention network connectivity with visual areas (figure 4).

Conclusion

The integration of functional and structural connectivity suggests the potential for developing a treatment response assessment mechanism. A task-based approach using unocular and complex visual acuity fMRI can complement the understanding of what changes to incorporate during treatment to improve efficacy in future interventions.

Figure 1: Baseline and Post therapy ROI network connectivity matrices in responders vs non-responder.

Figure 2: Visual Connectivity ROI changes in responders and non-responder.

Figure 3: Diffusion Connectivity connectome changes in FA observed is Responders vs Non responders.

Figure 4: Summary of Structural and functional correlate to clinical response.

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